

Stress and strain evolution during single-layer folding under pure and simple shear

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Abstract

Folds in rocks are commonly used in geology for strain analysis. They contain information about rock rheology, and the kinematics and mechanics of deformation. The systematic analysis of the evolution of stress and strain during rock folding can provide additional key information on the mechanical behaviour of rocks and the efficiency of the folding process. In order to investigate the evolution of rock rheology during fold development, a series of two-dimensional simulations of single-layer folding are presented here. They are run using the finite element method BASIL, integrated within the software platform ELLE, to simulate linear and non-linear viscous deformation. The kinematics of deformation, the competence ratio between the folding layer and surrounding matrix as well as the stress exponent of the power-law viscous material are systematically varied. The results allow comparing the stages of folding under different deformation kinematic conditions. For all simulations the folding amplification process starts when the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the competent layer deviates from the theoretical strain rate curve for a homogeneous material, which corresponds to a viscosity ratio between layer and matrix of $m=1$. The relative time when the fold amplification starts is determined by the viscosity ratio between the competent layer and its surrounding matrix, the initial layer orientation with respect to the shear plane, the kinematics of deformation and the stress exponent. The folding process is more effective in cases with high viscosity ratio, non-linear rheology and layers initially oriented at a low angle with respect to the shear plane, because the second invariant of the strain rate tensor at the layer deviates earlier from the theoretical curve. The results also show differences depending on the boundary conditions, where (1) folding a competent layer requires less work in simple shear than in pure shear, and (2) the geometrical softening experienced by the competent layer due to fold development is followed by a hardening stage in pure shear and by a major softening phase in simple shear. The simulation results suggest that the decrease of stress of a competent layer without decreasing the mechanical strength has a direct influence on the behaviour of a lithospheric layer around the crust-mantle boundary, which may experience geometrical softening depending on the tectonic settings rather than material softening due to metamorphic reactions or grain size reduction.

Keywords: Simple shear; pure shear; folding; strain estimation; vorticity; viscosity ratio; non-linear viscosity, geometrical softening.

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1. Introduction

One of the main aims of structural geology is to unravel rock deformation histories. Folds form as a response to compressional stress or shear stress. Fold patterns are widely used as indicators of

deformation kinematics, amount and orientation of strain and even viscosity contrast between folding layers and the surrounding rock matrix (Hudleston and Treagus, 2010; Llorens et al., 2013a; 2013b; Bobillo-Ares et al., 2004; Schmalholz and Mancktelow, 2016). Folds initiate from small perturbations at the interfaces between competent layers and matrix (*e.g.*, Ramberg, 1961; Ghosh, 1966; Sherwin and Chapple, 1968; Fletcher, 1974; Abassi and Mancktelow, 1992; Griera et al., 2018) and follow an exponential growth (Biot, 1961; Johnson and Fletcher 1994). According to previous rock fold studies, three stages of folding have been defined, termed (i) nucleation (or initial stage), when the layer is principally affected by layer-parallel homogeneous strain, (ii) amplification (or middle stage), when the limb dip and fold amplitude are increased rapidly, and (iii) kinematic growth (or late stage), when dynamic amplification of folds ceases and they become tight (Ghosh, 1993; Treagus, 1997; Schmalholz, 2006a; Hudleston and Treagus, 2010). To understand the development of folds, a large number of analytical studies (*e.g.*, Biot 1961, Sherwin and Chapple, 1968, Cobbold, 1971; 1975; Treagus and Treagus, 1981; Treagus, 1983;1999; Fletcher, 1991; Hudleston, 1993; Johnson and Fletcher, 1994; Schmalholz and Podladchikov, 2000), analogue experiments (*e.g.*, Hudleston, 1973; Cobbold, 1975; Manz and Wickham, 1978; Abassi and Mancktelow, 1992; Bons and Urai, 1996; Tikoff and Peterson, 1998) and field studies (Quinquis et al., 1978; Ramsay and Huber 1987; Ormond and Hudleston, 2003; Alsop et al., 2007; Alsop and Carreras, 2009; Mukherjee, 2014; Torremans et al., 2014; Pérez-Alonso et al., 2016) have been carried out during the last half century. Despite the fact that folding is a dynamic process characterised by large strain (Johnson and Fletcher, 1994; Turcotte and Schubert, 1982), most of the aforementioned analytical studies account for situations in which limb dips are very small, because they require a linearisation only applicable to the initial stages of folding. However, analytical and numerical studies of large-amplitude folding have been presented in the last ten years (see Schmalholz and Podladchikov, 2000; Adamuszek et al., 2013a; Llorens et al., 2013a; 2013b; 2014; Schmalholz and Mancktelow, 2016 and references therein).

Numerical simulations provide useful insights into the study of rock mechanics, as they allow modelling large-amplitude folding (relative to layer thickness). Complementary to field studies and analogue experiments, numerical simulations have been applied to investigate the nature and evolution of rock folding using finite difference methods (Zhang et al., 1996) and finite element methods (Zhang et al., 2000; Viola and Mancktelow, 2005; Schmid and Podladchikov, 2006), including the effect of non-linear rheology (Lan and Hudleston, 1991; Mancktelow, 1999; Schmalholz and Podladchikov, 2000; Llorens et al., 2013a; Llorens et al., 2013b), as well as three-dimensional folding (Zulauf and Zulauf, 2005; Kaus and Schmalholz, 2006; Schmid et al., 2008; Graseman and Schmalholz, 2012; Philippe, 2014). Most of the existing numerical studies focus on the geometrical evolution of folds (Cobbold, 1977; Lan and Huddlestone, 1995; Mancktelow, 1999; Huang et al., 2010; Llorens et al., 2013a; 2013b; Toimil and Griera, 2007), including a limited number of contributions that quantify the evolution of mechanical parameters during folding (Schmalholz et al., 2001; Jeng and Huang, 2008; Hobbs and Ord, 2012; Schmalholz and Maeder, 2012; Schmalholz and Schmid, 2012).

However, most of these studies deal with folding of layers in pure shear conditions, where the competent layer is oriented parallel to the maximum shortening direction and, therefore, layer-parallel strain is constant during deformation. But, in many cases in nature, layers are oriented obliquely with respect to the strain axes, where shearing and strain rate parallel to the layers evolve with progressive deformation. Folding of a layer oriented oblique to the maximum shortening direction has only been considered in a few cases (Cobbold, 1971; Treagus, 1973; Anthony and Wickham, 1978; Schmid 2002; Viola and Mancktelow, 2005), including the case of multilayer layer folding in simple shear (Schmalholz and Schmid, 2012). In Llorens et al. (2013a) a systematic numerical analysis of folding in pure and simple shear boundary conditions was presented, focusing on studying the differences in fold geometries between the two kinematic end-members. These simulations showed that, although there is no distinct visual difference between folds that formed in pure and simple shear, there is a noticeable difference in the refraction of foliation, which presents a

more complicated pattern in simple shear (see Llorens et al., 2013a; Ran et al., 2018). However, there is much more information that can potentially be obtained from the detailed analysis of the mechanical evolution of each system during folding.

This contribution systematically studies the mechanical evolution of large-amplitude folding both in pure and simple shear boundary conditions up to large deformation, in order to understand the mechanical behaviour of rocks and the effectiveness of folding according to the stress evolution. For this purpose, series of numerical simulations of folding of a single layer embedded in a softer matrix up to high strain are presented. The variation of stress and strain can be compared for different combinations of viscosity ratios, initial layer orientation, boundary conditions and stress exponent. By modelling the geometrical evolution of single-layer folds, together with the quantification of the stress and strain evolution of the system, the links between the rheological behaviour and the geometrical evolution of rocks are established for different stages of folding. This allows observing the geometrical softening of rocks and determining the efficiency of folding under different scenarios, and to reveal key information on the stages of fold evolution that can be applied to strain analysis in the field.

2. Methods

The models have been run with the software package ELLE (Jessell et al., 2001; Bons et al., 2008; Piazzolo et al., 2018; <http://www.elle.ws>), including the BASIL non-linear viscous finite element code (Houseman et al., 2008), to simulate single-layer folding in simple and pure shear boundary conditions. ELLE is a numerical platform for the simulation of the development of microstructures during tectonic and metamorphic processes. ELLE is based on the sequential coupling of different processes in a loop, which share the same data structure. BASIL is a finite element (FEM) deformation code that calculates non-linear viscous deformation of a 2D sheet in plane strain. BASIL is utilised to compute viscous strain rates and the associated stress fields. The form of the constitutive law relating the deviatoric stress tensor (τ_{ij}) to the strain rate tensor ($\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}$) for an incompressible viscous material is (Jessell et al., 2005):

$$\tau_{ij} = 2\eta\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = \eta \left[\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right] \quad (1)$$

where u is the velocity in either the x or y direction, and η is the viscosity that can be defined by:

$$\eta = \frac{B}{2} \dot{E}^{\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)-1} \quad (2)$$

where n denotes the strain rate exponent (linear viscous deformation if $n=1$), B is a material dependent parameter (proportional to the viscosity if $n=1$), and \dot{E} is the second invariant of the strain rate tensor.

In ELLE, the geometries of the folding layer and surrounding matrix are defined by a contiguous set of polygons, (termed “flynns”). Their boundaries are defined by boundary nodes (termed “bnodes”) that are connected by straight boundary segments (Fig. 1). In these numerical simulations each polygon has a homogeneous rheology. For simplicity, material dependent parameters B (eq.2) are kept constant throughout each simulation, without considering softening or hardening processes. A single competent layer embedded in a homogenous matrix has been used to create the starting microstructure (Fig.1). In simple shear simulations the layer is originally inclined at an angle (β) of 14° , 27° or 45° with respect to the shear plane (Fig. 1a). In this way the layer is vertical at a shear strain of $\gamma=4$, 2 or 1, respectively (Table 1). In pure shear boundary conditions, the layer is set parallel to the maximum shortening direction (Fig. 1b). The two-dimensional model corresponds to a dimensionless cell that has periodic horizontal and vertical boundaries. In simple shear simulations, the unit cell maintains a square shape with progressive deformation because it is repositioned after each deformation step (e.g., see Jessell et al., 2009). In pure shear simulations the model bounding box is not initially square, and changes during deformation (Fig. 1b).

Due to the wrapping boundaries, the initial configuration in simple shear effectively consists of multiple widely spaced layers, which become a single layer with a vertical envelope in the final stage, within the computational domain (Fig. 1a). Following the approach by Schmalholz and Podladchikov (2001), all the simulations presented in this paper have an initial random noise corresponding to a ratio between layer thickness (H) to amplitude (A) of 40. The initial perturbation is applied perpendicular to the layer for every boundary node, both in pure and simple shear simulations (for a detailed description of the layer noise application method see section 2.4. of Llorens et al., 2013a).

Fig. 1. Initial configuration and evolution of simulations in (a) simple shear and (b) pure shear, showing the final step at 75% of shortening. The competent layer is displayed in black and the soft matrix in white. The numerical models consist of two layers: (c) a polygon segment network of boundary nodes and (d) a Delaunay triangulation mesh. (e) Scheme of the ELLE workflow. The initial data structure goes through a closed loop of nine processes: shifty, reposition, elle2poly, non-linear viscous deformation BASIL, basil2elle, reposition, shifty, reposition, and a topology check. See section 2 for a complete description of each process.

The ELLE experimental workflow consists of a loop of nine individual processes (Fig. 1e). First, the initial data structure is shifted up by a random distance in the x or y axes (different in each time step), in order to minimise boundary effects associated with the application of velocity boundary conditions (effectively rigid plates at the top and bottom of the model). A random horizontal plane is chosen for shifting simple shear models while a vertical one is used for pure shear cases. Using this approach, the boundary conditions are applied at a different random level each time step and the resulting artefacts are therefore delocalised (Jessell et al., 2009). After this process, the model is subsequently repositioned to bring the nodes and elements back into the unit cell. The shifty and reposition ELLE-processes are called twice within the loop of each time step, *i.e.*, before and after the non-linear viscous deformation step.

Prior to the non-linear viscous FEM calculation (BASIL) each time step, the “elle2poly” ELLE process transforms the ELLE microstructure into a new Delaunay triangular mesh adapted to the layer boundaries (Fig. 1d). This constant remeshing process reduces the typical problems associated with highly deformed meshes. After BASIL, the “basil2elle” ELLE process converts the deformed Delaunay mesh back into the corresponding ELLE structure. After this process the model is repositioned to bring the nodes and elements back into the unit cell in the case of simple shear simulations.

Table 1
Simulation setup

Series name	Simulation name	Initial viscosity ratio (m)	Initial layer orientation (β)	Stress exponent (n)	Boundary conditions	Bulk shear strain (γ)	Layer short.
I	1	25	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
	2	50	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
	3	100	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
	4	150	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
	5	250	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
	6	500	14°	1	simple shear	4	75%
II	7	25	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
	8	50	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
	9	100	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
	10	150	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
	11	250	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
	12	500	27°	1	simple shear	2	55%
III	13	25	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
	14	50	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
	15	100	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
	16	150	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
	17	250	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
	18	500	45°	1	simple shear	1	37%
IV	19	25	14°	3	simple shear	4	75%
	20	50	14°	3	simple shear	4	75%
	21	100	14°	3	simple shear	4	75%
V	22	25	27°	3	simple shear	2	55%
	23	50	27°	3	simple shear	2	55%
	24	100	27°	3	simple shear	2	55%
VI	25	25	45°	3	simple shear	1	37%
	26	50	45°	3	simple shear	1	37%
	27	100	45°	3	simple shear	1	37%
VII	28	25	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
	29	50	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
	30	100	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
	31	150	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
	32	250	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
	33	500	0°	1	pure shear	0	75%
VIII	34	25	0°	3	pure shear	0	75%
	35	50	0°	3	pure shear	0	75%
	36	100	0°	3	pure shear	0	75%

Every step of deformation there is a constant incremental shear strain of $\gamma=0.025$ in simple shear or an equivalent 1% of incremental shortening in pure shear. At the end of the loop, an ELLE process of topology check takes place in order to avoid mesh problems, such as those arising when neighbour nodes get too close or too far away from each other.

In order to understand the effect of different conditions on the microstructure, the following parameters have been varied in the numerical simulation series (Table 1):

1. The initial viscosity ratio between layer and matrix ($m = 25, 50, 100, 150, 250$ and 500).

2. The initial layer orientation with respect to the shear plane ($\beta = 14^\circ, 27^\circ$ or 45°) in simple shear models.
3. The stress exponent of the non-linearity of viscosity ($n = 1$ or 3).
4. The boundary conditions (pure and simple shear).

3. Results

3.1. Series I, II and III: linear viscous simple shear simulations

These series of simulations have a starting configuration of a single layer with different viscosity ratios that range between $m=25$ and $m=500$ (Table 1). Different simulations with initial layer orientation (β) with respect to the shear plane have been performed (see Fig. 2 for examples of fold geometry evolution): Series I (Simulations 1 to 6) have an initial $\beta=14^\circ$. In these simulations the bulk shear strain (γ) is 4 and the layer is shortened 75% (Fig. 3a). Series II (Simulations 7 to 12) have an initial orientation of $\beta=27^\circ$ with a bulk shear strain (γ) of 2, and the layer is shortened 55% of its initial length (Fig. 3b). Series III (Simulations 13 to 18) have an initial layer orientation of $\beta=45^\circ$, the bulk shear strain (γ) is 1 and the layer is shortened 37% (Fig. 3c).

Fig. 2. Progressive shortening up to 75% of shortening of a single layer folding in simple shear for two viscosity ratio (m) end-members in Series I of (a) 500 and (b) 25 and stress exponent of $n=1$.

Fig. 3. Second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ versus layer shortening for linear ($n=1$) simple shear simulations with initial layer orientations with respect to the shear plane of (a) $\beta=14^\circ$ (Series I), (b) $\beta=27^\circ$ (Series II) (c) $\beta=45^\circ$ (Series III) and (d) pure shear simulations (Series VII). Mohr circles for flow and sketch of the initial layer orientations for (e) simple shear simulations (Series I, II and III) and (f) pure shear simulations (Series VII). Each point in the Mohr circle indicate the angular velocity ($\dot{\omega}$) and the theoretical strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}' = \dot{\epsilon}_1 \sin(2\beta)$ where $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ is the maximum strain rate. The evolution for simulations with viscosity ratio (m) from 25 to 500 is plotted showing the deviation with respect to the theoretical strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) for a homogeneous material (black line). $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ values are normalised respect to the bulk flow $\langle \dot{E}_{bulk} \rangle$. Theoretical strain rate values are normalised respect to the maximum strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_1$, and therefore correspond to $\dot{\epsilon} = \sin(2\beta)$. Please note that the theoretical strain rate line for pure shear ($\beta=0$) has a constant value of 1 in the graph. Examples of layer geometry at different steps of shortening for simulations of series I are presented in Figure 2.

All the simulations performed here start with a stage in which the layer experiences thickening until a certain wavelength of perturbation is selectively amplified, and fold amplification begins (Fig. 3). The thickening process can be determined following the second invariant of the strain rate tensor $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ for a homogeneous material, where the viscosity ratio between the layer and matrix is $m=1$ (black line in Fig. 3). The second invariant of the strain rate tensor is calculated from averaged

strain rate components in the layer. According to the Mohr circle for flow, the strain rate evolution for a homogeneous material corresponds to the theoretical strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1 \sin 2\beta$, where $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ is the maximum strain rate and β the orientation of the layer with respect to the maximum compression axis (Fig. 3e-f). The construction of the Mohr circle for flow is carried out based on the relationship between the angular velocity ($\dot{\omega}$) and the strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$). A horizontal diagonal through the circle defines the maximum and minimum strain rates, $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_2$ (Lister and Williams, 1983; Passchier, 1986, 1988, 1990). In both pure and simple shear simulations, the maximum and minimum strain axes are parallel and perpendicular to the layer, respectively (see $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ direction in the layer in Fig. 4) and therefore, in all simulations $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ is equivalent to the layer-parallel strain rate.

In all simulations the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ follows the theoretical strain rate curve during the thickening process, regardless the layer competence or its initial orientation. When the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer reaches its highest value, deviating afterwards from the theoretical curve, the amplification process starts. The amount of thickening before folding is determined by the viscosity ratio (m), in a way that at high values the deviation is reached early (see purple $m=500$ line in Figs. 3a-c), while at low viscosity ratio the layer is affected by more intense thickening (see light blue $m=25$ curve in Figs. 3a-c). The effect of the viscosity ratio on the amount of layer thickening is clearly observable following the fold patterns during folding (compare Figs. 2a and 2b).

Fig. 4. Second invariant of the strain rate tensor $\langle \dot{E} \rangle$ field of linear-viscous simulations deformed under (a) pure shear and (b-d) different steps of shear strain (γ) in simple shear. The dashed lines indicate the direction of the principal strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_1$), which is oriented parallel to the layer in simple shear during deformation. The viscosity ratio is $m=25$ for both pure and simple shear simulations.

In simple shear deformation the second invariant of the strain rate tensor $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ depends on the layer orientation. In Series III simulations $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ only decreases, following a similar evolution as that of the theoretical strain rate curve for a homogeneous material (Fig. 3c), thus resulting in a less effective folding process. In these simulations, the layer is initially oriented at 45° with respect to the shear plane, where the strain rate is equivalent to the maximum strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ (see the Mohr circle for flow in Fig. 3e). When the initial layer is oriented at a low angle (β) with respect to the shear plane, as in Series I ($\beta=14^\circ$) and II ($\beta=27^\circ$) (Fig. 3c), $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ increases first and then decreases after it deviates from the theoretical strain rate curve. At high viscosity ratio (see $m \geq 150$ in Fig. 6a) the maximum deviatoric shear stress in the layer first increases, up to ca. 10% of shortening, and strongly decreases afterwards. When the viscosity ratio is reduced the initial stress increase stage decreases, resulting in a constant maximum deviatoric shear stress during deformation in cases of low viscosity ratio (see curve of $m \leq 100$ in Fig. 6a).

In simple shear deformation, the development of folds depends on the initial orientation of the layer with respect to the shear plane (β). For the same amount of bulk shear strain, layers initially oriented at low β fold more effectively than those initially oriented at high β (compare $\gamma=1$ for simulations 4, 10 and 16 in Fig. 5b-d). A layer oriented at a low angle with respect to the shear

plane deviates from the theoretical pattern (see $\beta=14^\circ$ or 27° in Fig. 5a). However, when oriented at a high angle the $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ its evolution follows the theoretical curve (see $\beta=45^\circ$ in Fig. 5a). The Mohr circle for flow reveals that when the layer is initially oriented at a low angle with respect to the shear plane (Simulation 4) the strain rate increases up to a maximum value ($\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1 \sin 2\beta$), which is reached when the layer is oriented at $\beta=45^\circ$. However, when the layer is initially oriented at a high angle with respect to the shear plane (Simulation 16), it starts with the maximum value, $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1$, and decreases during deformation (see comparison of the three simulations presented plotted in the Mohr circle for flow Fig. 5f).

Fig. 5. (a) Second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ versus layer orientation for simple shear simulations with viscosity $m=150$ and stress exponent $n=1$ with different initial layer orientation (β) with respect to the shear plane. The evolution of the $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ is plotted showing the deviation with respect to the theoretical strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1 \sin(2\beta)$ (grey line). Progressive shortening of simulations with an initial layer orientation of (b) $\beta=14^\circ$ (Simulation 4), (c) $\beta=27^\circ$ (Simulation 10) and (d) $\beta=45^\circ$ (Simulation 16). (e) Mohr circle for flow for Simulations 4, 10 and 16. $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ values are normalised with respect to the bulk flow $\langle \dot{E}_{bulk} \rangle$. Theoretical strain rate values are normalised with respect to the maximum strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_1$, and therefore correspond to $\dot{\epsilon} = \sin(2\beta)$.

Fig. 6. Layer maximum deviatoric shear stress *versus* layer shortening for simulations with stress exponent (a) $n=1$ (Series I and VII) and (b) $n=3$ (Series IV and VIII). (c) Mohr circle of flow for pure and simple shear simulations. Stress values are normalised with respect to the maximum layer-averaged deviatoric stress in the linear and non-linear simulations, respectively.

3.2. Series VII: Pure shear simulations with linear viscous deformation

This series of simulations has a starting configuration of a single layer with different viscosity ratios that vary from $m=25$ to 500 (Series VII in Table 1). In these simulations the layer is initially oriented parallel to the maximum compression axis (Fig. 1b) and it is deformed in pure shear up to 75% of shortening. Note that for these conditions (pure shear deformation and $\beta=0^\circ$) the theoretical strain rate for a homogeneous material is constant, as it is equivalent to the radius of the Mohr circle for flow, which corresponds to the maximum strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_1$) (Fig. 3f).

At the beginning of deformation, all presented pure shear simulations follow the theoretical strain rate curve. During this stage, the layer thickens (Figs. 3d and 7a,b). When the amplification process starts the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer decreases and deviates from the theoretical curve. As in simple shear simulations, the deviation from the theoretical curve is determined by the competence of the layer with respect to the matrix (*e.g.*, see comparison of $m=25$ and $m=500$ curves in Figs. 3d and 7b). Under pure shear conditions the second invariant of the strain rate tensor ($\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$) decreases during deformation, which is similar to the behaviour of a layer oriented at $\beta=45^\circ$ with respect to the shear plane in simple shear (Series III) (Fig. 3c,d). In both situations ($\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$) starts at its highest value and decreases during deformation due the initial orientation of the layer with respect to the maximum compression axis (Fig. 3e,f).

Fig. 7. Progressive shortening of single-layer folding in pure shear for two viscosity ratios (m) end members of Series VII of (a) $m=500$ and (b) $m=25$, and stress exponent of $n=1$. Fold geometries are relatively similar to those in simulations performed in simple shear with layer initially oriented at a low angle with respect to the shear plane (see Fig. 2).

At high viscosity ratio the layer's maximum deviatoric shear stress in pure shear is almost that for simple shear simulations (compare solid and dashed lines for $m \geq 150$ in Fig. 6a), while at low

viscosity ratios differences cannot be observed (compare solid and dashed lines for $m \leq 100$ in Fig. 6a).

3.4. Series IV, V, VI and VIII: non-linear viscous deformation simulations

In order to investigate the effect of the non-linearity of deformation, I ran additional simulations with a stress exponent (n) of three using the same initial configuration as that of the linear viscous simulations described above. Initial viscosity ratios between layer and matrix (m) of 25, 50 and 100 were used for this simulation series (Series IV, V, VI and VIII in Table 1).

The evolution of non-linear simulations is similar to that of linear ones in all cases. However, folds become more visible at a lower strain in non-linear simulations. The stress exponent effectively raises the viscosity ratio between the competent layer and the soft matrix (Jessell et al., 2009; Llorens et al., 2013a) (Fig.10d and 11d). The evolution of the true layer viscosity, defined as the ratio between the layer-parallel deviatoric stress to twice the layer-parallel strain rate ($\mu_t = \frac{\sigma_1}{2\dot{\epsilon}_1}$) (Schmalholz et al., 2005), is shown in Figure 12. In linear viscous simulations, the true layer viscosity is constant during deformation. In non-linear viscous simulations the true layer viscosity is increased during deformation. At the end of the simulations, for an initial viscosity ratio of $m=25$ the true layer viscosity is double in non-linear models compared to linear cases. This increment becomes much higher in simulations with an initial viscosity ratio of $m=100$, where the true layer viscosity is above $\mu_t = 400$. This higher viscosity ratio is observable if one compares the deviation point to the theoretical curve, which is reached earlier for the same initial viscosity ratio m in non-linear simulations than in linear ones (compare Figs. 3a-c with 8a-c). For example, Simulations 3, 5 and 6 (see $m=100, 250$ and 500 in Fig. 3a) are comparable with Simulations 19, 20 and 21 (see $m=25, 50$ and 100 in Fig. 8a), respectively. In non-linear viscous simulations, the layer maximum deviatoric shear stress remains higher in pure shear than in simple shear (Fig. 6b). As in the case of linear simulations, this difference is reduced at low viscosity ratio.

Fig. 8. Second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ versus layer shortening for non-linear ($n=3$) simple shear simulations with initial layer orientation with respect to the shear plane of (a) $\beta=14^\circ$ (Series IV), (b) $\beta=27^\circ$ (Series V) (c) $\beta=45^\circ$ (Series VI) and (d) pure shear conditions (Series VIII). Mohr circle for flow and sketch of the initial layer orientations for (e) simple shear simulations (Series IV, V and VI) and (f) pure shear simulations (Series VIII). Each point in the Mohr circle indicates the angular velocity ($\dot{\omega}$) and the theoretical strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1 \sin(2\beta)$ where $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ is the maximum strain rate. The evolution for simulations with viscosity ratio (m) from 25 to 100 is plotted showing the deviation with respect to the theoretical strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) for a homogeneous material (black line). $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ values are normalised with respect to the bulk flow $\langle \dot{E}_{bulk} \rangle$. Theoretical strain rate values are normalised with respect to the maximum strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_1$, and therefore correspond to $\dot{\epsilon} = \sin(2\beta)$. Please note that the theoretical strain rate line for pure shear ($\beta=0$) has a constant value of 1 in the graph.

3.5. Second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer versus fold geometry

It is the aim of this study to link the rheological behaviour with the resulting fold geometry during the folding process. The competence ratio between layer and matrix, amount of shortening, boundary conditions and non-linearity of deformation determine the rheological response and corresponding final shape of folded competent layers. For this purpose, the results of mechanical analysis presented in this contribution are linked with a previous study of folding parameters

already measured (see Llorens et al., 2013a). Figure 9 shows the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer together with the fold pattern evolution, where the different stages of folding are observed. As shown in figure 9, the duration of the nucleation stage has a first-order influence on the final thickness of the folded layer. The duration of the nucleation stage varies depending on the boundary conditions, where simple shear deformation has a larger nucleation stage (compare Figs. 9a-c with 9d-f). This effect is more pronounced at low viscosity ratio ($m=25$), where the thickness (H) of the folded layer reaches much higher values in simple shear than in pure shear deformation (Fig. 9a,d). Regardless the boundary conditions, when the viscosity ratio is higher ($m=100$) the nucleation stage is reduced, and therefore layers thicken less and follow a similar trend in both pure and simple shear simulations (see shadow trend in Fig. 9c,f).

Fig. 9. Evolution of the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ (blue solid line) at different steps of layer shortening (in red), marking the stages of folding: n (nucleation), a (amplification) and k (kinematic growth) for linear ($n=1$) simulations performed in (a-c) pure shear and (d-f) simple shear with different viscosity ratio (m). Fold parameters of ratios of A/λ and H/λ

are indicated in light grey shading (from Llorens et al., 2013a). Final geometry (at 75% of shortening) of folded layer is shown down right.

In viscous single-layer folding, the growth rate (α) normalised with respect to the initial growth rate (α_0) is expressed as the rate between the membrane stress averaged over the layer thickness ($P(\varepsilon)$) and the initial compressive membrane stress (P_0). As the membrane stress is proportional to the layer-parallel stress (σ), the growth rate can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_0} = \frac{P(\varepsilon)}{P_0} = \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{01}} \quad (3)$$

The nucleation amplitude (A_n) is calculated from the layer-parallel stress, where $A_n=1/(2\alpha)$. Figure 13 shows the corresponding A_n with respect to the effective dominant wavelength (λ_{eff}) defined by Schmalholz and Podladchikov (2001), for the presented simulations. The results show a similar trend as the analytical solution provided by these authors, where decreasing λ_{eff} values cause larger nucleation amplitudes and, therefore, larger nucleation stages.

Fig. 10. Maximum deviatoric shear stress, second invariant of the strain rate tensor and logarithmic viscosity of linear-viscous simple shear simulations with viscosity ratio (a) $m=25$ (Simulation 1), (b) $m=50$ (Simulation 2), (c) $m=100$ (Simulation 3), and non-linear viscous simulation with viscosity ratio (d) $m=50$ (Simulation 20) at shear strain of $\gamma=2$ and $\gamma=4$.

Fig. 11. Maximum deviatoric shear stress, second invariant of the strain rate tensor and logarithmic viscosity of linear-viscous pure shear simulations with viscosity ratio (a) $m=25$ (Simulation 28), (b) $m=50$ (Simulation 29), (c) $m=100$ (Simulation 30), and non-linear viscous simulation with viscosity ratio (d) $m=50$ (Simulation 35) at steps of 45% and 75% of shortening.

During the nucleation stage the second invariant of the strain rate tensor $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ is increased in simple shear, while it remains constant in pure shear (compare n stage in Figs. 9a-c with 9d-f). In both pure and simple shear simulations, the amplification stage (a stage in Fig. 9) starts with a decrease in the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer. However, at the kinematic growth stage (k stage in Fig. 9), where limb dips are tight, the $\langle \dot{E}_{layer} \rangle$ is increased in pure shear, while a major decrease is observed in simple shear simulations. At the kinematic growth stage, where the layer is close to an orientation perpendicular to the shear plane ($\gamma=4$) the maximum deviatoric shear stress in the matrix is almost equal to that inside the competent layer (see $\gamma=4$ in Fig. 10a-c), while in pure shear the maximum deviatoric shear stress is higher in the matrix (see 75% of shortening in Fig. 11a-c).

4. Discussion

Folds in a single layer can develop due to rheological anisotropy (Cobbold et al., 1971; Jansen et al., 2016; Bons et al., 2016) or due to a viscosity contrast between the layer and the surrounding matrix. Single-layer folding caused by rheological anisotropy results in the formation of similar folds (Ramsay and Huber, 1987), and folding caused by a contrast of viscosity between the layer and matrix (*i.e.*, buckle folding) results in the development of parallel folds (Hudleston and Treagus, 2010). Ghosh (1993) and Treagus (1997) defined the stages of buckle folding as: (1) fold nucleation, (2) fold amplification and (3) fold kinematic growth. Schmalholz (2006a) more accurately defined these three stages, including the effect of the viscosity ratio and the initial layer perturbation on fold pattern evolution. The present study allows observing the mechanical evolution during the different folding stages for competent layers embedded in a softer matrix, deformed under different boundary conditions. In the present simulations one can visualise the fold nucleation stage in detail, since it is observable by looking at the deviation of the second invariant of the strain rate tensor from the theoretical trend for a homogeneous material ($m=1$). This stage directly depends on the viscosity ratio (m) between the layer and matrix. In natural rocks, the absence of folding would indicate a very low viscosity ratio between phases (Hansen and Warren, 2015), since folding occurs even at low viscosity contrast (Hudleston, 1973; Llorens et al., 2013a). When the viscosity ratio between layer and matrix is low, the thickening stage is longer than that in cases of high viscosity ratio. The deviation from the theoretical curve is reached earlier at lower strain in non-linear than in linear simulations, because the stress exponent ($n>1$) raises the viscosity ratio between the competent layer and the soft matrix. The thickening stage of the simulations presented in this contribution follows a similar evolution than that predicted by Schmalholz and Podladchikov (2001), where the analytical solution for the nucleation amplitude versus effective dominant wavelength (λ_{eff}) was provided. In agreement with the analytical solution, the simulations show that the nucleation amplitude, and therefore the thickening stage, increase strongly when λ_{eff} decreases (Fig.13). However, numerical simulations reveal that the nucleation amplitude is higher in simple shear, being the thickening stage larger than that in pure shear simulations (Fig.13a-b). This type of evolution, in which there is initial thickening and subsequent buckling, has already been described in natural examples (*e.g.*, Torremans et al., 2014; Pérez-Alonso et al., 2016).

Fig.12. Evolution of the true layer viscosity, defined as the ratio between the layer-parallel deviatoric stress to twice layer-parallel strain rate ($\mu_t = \frac{\sigma_1}{2\dot{\epsilon}_1}$), for linear-viscous (Series VII) and non-linear viscous (Series VIII) pure shear simulations.

Fig.13. Nucleation amplitude (A_N) versus effective dominant wavelength (λ_{eff}) defined by Schmalholz and Podladchikov (2001), for (a) pure and (b) simple shear simulations. Linear and non-linear simulations are plotted in dashed lines. Solid line corresponds to the analytical solution provided by Schmalholz and Podladchikov (2001). The nucleation amplitude indicates the end of the nucleation stage, where the layer thickening dominates.

In the simple shear simulations presented here, the second invariant of the strain rate tensor follows the layer-parallel strain rate, as the maximum and minimum strain axes are parallel and perpendicular to the layer, respectively (Fig.4b-d). This is caused by the partitioning of vorticity in heterogeneous materials (Means et al., 1980; Lister and Williams, 1983). Natural examples of deformation partitioning can be found in shear zones, where fabric studies indicate that flow partitioning occurs when there is a competence contrast in the deformed rocks (Lister and Williams, 1979; Schoneveld, 1979).

The simulations reveal that the evolution of the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer is different depending on the boundary conditions. Here the mechanical evolution of simple shear systems is compared, for first time, with those in pure shear, in which strain rate is constant because only layer-parallel shortening is considered. When comparing simulations run in pure and simple shear boundary conditions, one can observe that the evolution of the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer differs during the initial nucleation process, where an increase occurs in simple shear (*i.e.*, strain hardening) while it remains constant in pure shear (see a comparison of the evolution of the system before the deviation from the theoretical curve for pure and simple shear simulations in Fig.3a). Once the deviation point is reached, the second invariant of the strain rate tensor significantly decreases (*i.e.*, the layer softens) in both simple and pure shear conditions. When a single layer is deformed under pure shear shortening with a constant background strain rate, the deviatoric layer-parallel stress, and therefore the layer-parallel strain rate, decrease. As the effective viscosity (μ_{eff}) of the layer is defined as the ratio of the layer-parallel deviatoric stress to twice the background strain rate ($\mu_{eff} = \frac{\sigma_1}{2\dot{\epsilon}_b}$), a decrease in layer-parallel deviatoric stress (or layer-parallel strain rate) implies a decrease in the effective viscosity of the layer (Schmalholz et al., 2005; Schmalholz et al., 2006b), representing geometrical softening. For the simple shear simulations presented here, the background strain rate is not constant, as it grows until the layer is oriented at 45° with respect to the shear plane. However, for all simple shear cases shown in this contribution, the decrease in layer-parallel strain rate occurs before the layer reaches the 45° orientation with respect to the shear plane. Therefore, this decrease represents a reduction in the effective viscosity as in pure shear simulations. For non-linear simulations the true layer viscosity is strain-rate dependent and higher than that in linear cases. However, the decrease in layer-parallel strain rate observed would indicate a geometrical softening by the reduction of the effective viscosity with respect to the true layer viscosity, as in linear cases. This geometrical softening is caused by the development of folds due structural instabilities. The geometrical or structural

softening caused by active folding has been previously described in multilayers deformed under pure shear conditions (Schmalholz et al., 2005; Schmalholz and Schmid, 2012).

The presented results for pure shear simulations have a similar evolution as that predicted in Schmalholz (2005) and Schmalholz (2006b), where the analytical solution for the strain rate evolution in the layer during folding under pure shear deformation is provided. In these contributions the structural softening is studied as the evolution of the ratio between the layer-parallel strain rate and the background shortening for different viscosity ratios (see Fig. 3B in Schmalholz et al., 2005 and Fig.7 in Schmalholz, 2006b). The ratio between the layer-parallel strain rate and the background pure shear shortening also represents the ratio of the effective layer viscosity to the true layer viscosity (see eq.2 in Schmalholz et al., 2005). The decrease in effective viscosity predicted by the analytical finite amplitude solution, (FAS, Schmalholz and Podladchikov, 2000) can be higher than one order of magnitude. The analytical predictions are coincident with the results of pure shear simulations presented in this contribution, where the decrease in the second invariant of the strain rate tensor experienced by the layer is around one order of magnitude (see fig.3d). The geometrical softening of folding is expected to be followed by a hardening stage once the limb dips are higher than 45° (Adamuszek et al., 2013b). In pure shear simulations strain rate is constant and the expected hardening process is clearly observed at the kinematic growth stage. However, in simple shear simulations the layer orientation with respect to the shear plane varies with progressive deformation and, therefore, strain rate is not constant. At the kinematic growth stage, the layer approaches an orientation perpendicular to the shear plane, where the layer strain rate is minimum, and the stress experienced by the layer is almost equal to that experienced by the matrix. This effect is observed in simple shear simulations by a higher softening at the kinematic growth stage.

Softening processes have a key impact on the deformation of the lithosphere. A variation in mineral rock composition or grain size reduction occurs in the lithosphere at depth (Brace and Kohlstedt, 1980; Kohlstedt et al., 1995). This change in rheological properties can produce material softening (Braun et al., 1999; Huisman and Beaumont, 2003). However, as revealed in the present contribution, the development of folds associated with layer instabilities, as expected in lithospheric layers, can produce geometrical softening while the rheological properties are kept constant. As shown in Schmalholz et al. (2005), the structural instabilities have a first-order impact on the softening of the competent lithospheric layer around the crust-mantle boundary during compressive tectonic settings.

Simulations performed in simple shear with the layer initially oriented at low angle with respect to the shear plane develop similar fold patterns than those performed in pure shear conditions. However, at the beginning of the simulations in simple shear the strain rate of the layer is approximately half of the strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1/2$) that in pure shear cases ($\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_1$), due to the different initial layer orientation with respect to the deformation axes. As a result, the layer maximum deviatoric shear stress is considerably lower in simulations under simple shear than in pure shear cases. When the viscosity ratio is increased the layer maximum deviatoric shear stress is almost double in pure shear than in simple shear simulations, leading to similar fold patterns in both cases. Therefore, folding a competent layer requires less work in simple shear than under pure shear boundary conditions.

5. Conclusions

This contribution presents a systematic study of folding of a competent layer deformed in pure and simple shear boundary conditions up to high strain. The viscosity ratio between layer and matrix (m), the stress exponent (n) of the power-law viscous materials and the initial layer orientation (β) with respect to the shear plane (in simple shear) are systematically varied. This approach allows comparing the mechanics of folding and analysing the stress and strain evolution during the

different stages of folding. In all simulations the point where the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer deviates from the theoretical strain rate curve for a homogeneous material can be observed. Simulations reveal that the viscosity ratio, initial layer orientation and non-linearity of viscosity have a first-order impact on the folding process, because they determine when the second invariant of the strain rate tensor in the layer deviates from the theoretical strain rate curve. The comparison of folding mechanics in pure and simple shear conditions reveals that the duration of the nucleation stage is larger in simple shear, resulting in more layer thickening than in pure shear. The analysis of the maximum deviatoric shear stress inside the layers indicates that folding a competent layer requires less work in simple shear than in pure shear. The geometrical softening caused by the development of folds is clearly observed in pure and simple shear simulations. However, due to the layer orientation with respect to the deformation axes, layer softening is followed by hardening in pure shear or a major softening stage in simple shear. The simulation results suggest that the behaviour of a lithospheric layer around the crust-mantle boundary may experience geometrical softening depending on the tectonic settings rather than material softening due metamorphic reactions or grain size reduction.

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